

Understanding user needs for robotics assisted cognitive and physical rehabilitation

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Abstract— Biorobotics assistance to rehabilitation has the potential to benefit patients and clinicians significantly, helping to improve outcomes and support clinician users in key task while promoting their sustainability. However significant barriers to a widespread adoption of robotics technologies in clinical practice still exist. For these reasons, as one of the kick-off activities of the Fit4MedRob project, we have performed a literature mapping study to inform the design and execution of a large national survey aimed at identifying unmet user needs, barriers of currently available solutions, and key requirements for biorobotics devices supporting physical and cognitive rehabilitation. The survey results will constitute the cornerstone of research, implementation and evaluation activities of the project and significantly contribute to foster the translation of biorobotics from the experimental setting to established practice in the Italian rehabilitation services landscape.

Keywords— biorobotics, cognitive rehabilitation, physical rehabilitation, requirements.

I. INTRODUCTION

BIOROBOTICS, i.e. a melting pot of technologies spanning from bioengineering to robotics, including artificial intelligence, controls, sensors, smart materials, has been proposed as an appealing option to improve the clinical outcome of physical rehabilitation and personal care treatments in a sustainable manner. This because of the unique combination of features offered by robots: they host sensors and computational reasoning to understand and decipher environmental or patient intentions, and they have physical bodies able to perform actions in response to such reasoning. However, significant clinical, organizational and socioeconomic issues still exist for a wide and successful employment of biorobotics in healthcare and rehabilitation. For example, current rehabilitation and assistive models offered by the Italian national healthcare system lack in personalization and adequate continuum of care throughout all the phases of the rehabilitation process. Hence, excluding few exceptions nationwide, rehabilitation outcomes are typically unsatisfactory for the patients albeit expensive to the system.

For these reasons, a large consortium of 11 academic 11 clinical research centres and 3 companies has been created in December 2022 in response to the Italian national initiative on biorobotics, rehabilitation and digital technologies.

A. Background

Fit for Medical Robots - A new generation of biorobotic and digital technologies for a sustainable welfare (F4MR) is the name of the large project consortium, comprising 25 partners, funded by the Italian Ministry of University and Research

(MUR), to achieve the above-mentioned goals within a time-horizon of four years.

The project is organized in the Hub and Spokes fashion, with three spokes each corresponding to a project mission. Spoke 1, co-coordinated by the University of Pavia and the Don Gnocchi Foundation, focuses on the pivotal mission of clinical translation and innovation (see Fig.1). Spoke 1 aims to run extensive, in terms of number of patients and/or duration, multi-centric, clinical trials using healthcare or personal care robots that are currently available or developed by the F4MR consortium. Besides identifying their clinical efficacy and evidence (and limits), such treatments will also be assessed in terms of generated value from the perspectives of the involved stakeholders (final users and their families, workers and healthcare professionals, hospital facilities, payers, e.g., insurers, healthcare systems, etc.). In parallel, pivotal actions aimed at understanding and overcoming current legal barriers within the healthcare system will be implemented.

Fig. 1: Overall organization of the F4MR project, its three missions and their inter-relations. This article focuses on the first activity of Mission 1, dedicated to the elicitation of unmet user (both clinician and patient) needs to foster wider adoption.

B. Objective

One of the first objectives of the spoke 1 of Fit4MedRob is to carry out a thorough user (both patients and clinicians) needs elicitation and analysis, to inform development of new systems during the project, improve existing devices, perform sound impact, cost and sustainability evaluation of biorobotics applications, and foster their wider adoption in clinical practice. For this purpose, a literature review of questionnaires used to elicit requirements of robotics-assisted rehabilitation has been performed, in order to develop a F4MR-specific survey instrument to be distributed in the consortium. The overarching objective of the two activities is to collect requirements that can inform the remainder of the F4MR project phases.

Fig. 2: A conceptual visualization of the user needs and requirements identified in the literature review, organized in 6 macro categories. The figure reports (in blue) the number of articles in our review mentioning/supporting the specific requirement.

In this paper we present the results achieved by the first 2 months of spoke 1 activities, and preview a preliminary version of the formal requirements collection instrument we plan to use for identification of unmet user needs and barriers preventing widespread adoption of currently available device.

METHODS

In order to cover both peer-reviewed as well as grey literature (e.g. industry whitepapers or informal surveys), Google Scholar was searched using the following query: *requirements AND robot AND rehabilitation AND (survey OR questionnaire)*.

Since the retrieved results were quite scarce, we did not apply further filtering based on time of publication. Additional inclusion criteria consisted in:

- The paper included a requirements analysis aimed at therapists and patients (both or either one)
- The article is not a review of the effectiveness of the rehabilitation robot itself.

Roughly 50 papers were screened by title and abstract, and only 12 were actually selected for full-text analysis and further used to inform our research and F4MR instrument design.

II. RESULTS

A total of 53 requirements, summarized in Fig.2, have been identified from the selected articles. After reviewing the requirements 6 categories were created: Structural (n = 17), Software (n = 12), Functional (n = 6), Safety (n = 8), Cost (n = 4), Other (n = 6). It is worth mentioning that some requirements naturally belong to multiple categories. For

instance, “user friendliness” is meant as a general concept and should also be included in software requirements, on top of the reported categorization in structural requirements that we adopted for Fig.2. In the following we expand on a selection of requirements we identified for the different categories, and discuss the key findings of the review together with their relevance for F4MR.

A. Structural Requirements

A common theme among the interviews conducted in the reviewed articles, is the need for the therapeutic robot to fit the needs of as many patients as possible [1]–[6] (Non-Specificity), this included taking into account the physical characteristics of patients, such as age, weight, disabilities etc., but also to include the specific exercises needed for their therapy (High DOFs[1]–[3], [5], [7], [8], High repetition[2]–[4], [9], Usable in a seated[2], [3], [9] or standing position[3]).

One frequent complaint was about the difficulty of using the robot (User Friendly)[1], [2], [5], [7], [8], [10], but also the long and complex process of set-up[1]–[4], [10], donning and doffing[1], [2], [4], [6], [7]. Many therapists felt that they wouldn’t consider robot therapy if the initial steps required to use it were too time consuming[2], [4].

Other relevant requirements to take into consideration are comfort[1], [2], [6], stability[1]–[3], [7], [9] and focus (No distracting sounds)[6] of patients using the robot.

When it comes to Home-Based robots, there were some conflicting opinions, where some believed that a domicile robot could help with the amount of therapy performed by patients[1], others believed that and independent use wasn’t recommended due to incorrect use, overuse and over reliance[1].

Nonetheless a semi-supervised use was generally seen as positive[1], [3], [4], [10], with some suggesting the possibility of group therapy[4].

B. Functional Requirements

While using the therapeutic robot there should be a clear link to the Activities of Daily Living[2]–[4], [9]–[11] such as grooming, personal hygiene, feeding oneself etc. It is also important to allow for goal-oriented therapy[2] specific to each patient.

C. Software Requirements

Patient monitoring is seen as a critical need by therapists[2], [6], [8]. In order to do so it is mandatory to gather patient-specific data[1], [2], [4], [8] on therapy sessions and configurations for donning. It goes without saying that this data mustn’t be modified by users, therefore data access authority is required[1], [8].

Motivation is also quite important[1], [4], [7], [10], and many believe that robots can help by providing feedback to patients (and therapists alike) [1], [2], [4], [8], [10], gamification[1]–[3] (even though some are against using it[1]) and by making the exterior of the robot attractive[12].

Another somewhat important detail is being compatible with other software, such as notes, billing/insurance [8] etc.

D. Safety Requirements

Obviously, Safety regulations must be followed. The main concerns for safety requirements were about misuse of the device, especially if it allows unsupervised use by patients. In

order to make it safer there must be a kill switch[1], [8], alarm systems with sounds and messages[1], [8], and it must slowly return in a safe position whenever an error occurs[8]. Mechanical safety should be guaranteed[1], [6] (no finger traps etc.) at all times.

E. Cost Requirements

Many complained that the devices were too expensive[2], not cost effective[10], and often weren’t even eligible for refund by the public healthcare system[1].

Some papers also investigated how much money the therapist/institutions were willing to spend[1], [3], [9] to acquire or use the device, but the prices were heavily dependent from the country where the study was conducted and the economic situation at the specific times of the survey/interviews.

F. Other Requirements

Providing adequate Assistance[1], [2] and Training[10] should be taken into consideration when developing a robotic device. Some patients weren’t too sure how to feel about the robotic device since they were afraid it might look too technical[6]. Therefore it is important to make sure the patients do not feel scared by the robot[5], and findings suggest that if the use is recommended by therapist[10] himself it helps with patient acceptance and feelings towards the device.

G. F4MR user needs elicitation study

In the immediate future we will implement our own survey instrument using a web-based questionnaire solution, inspired both by the findings of the present literature mapping study and by comparable (albeit more narrow-scoped) studies like ECAD’s RehaTech4Child Survey[13].

The requirements elicitation instrument that will be the basis of the user needs identification study of F4MR has the following structure, and investigates key constructs identified in this review:

- Questions about demographics and work experience. Other than therapists, we will also include engineers as part of our respondents.
- Did you already use robotic devices for therapy purposes?
 - o If the answer is yes, questions about their experiences and opinions with robotic devices will follow.

In particular, for each device listed, a set of questions extrapolated from the present literature mapping study will be asked. Although the primary subjects of the F4MR project are patients with certain illnesses, such as CNS and PNS injuries and disorders, people at risk of occupational diseases and the frail elderly are also included.

Furthermore, it is of special interest the effects that robot therapy has had on paediatric patients.

Therefore, knowing what kind of patient these machines were subjected to, what the objectives of robotic rehabilitation were and whether they were actually met, will be crucial.

- Otherwise, we will expand on their knowledge and beliefs on robotic devices and if they wish to use them.

III. CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this article was to present a list of requirements and unmet user needs for the development, improvement and evaluation of therapeutic robots for rehabilitation. We performed a literature mapping study to inform a project-specific instrument development, and inform subsequent phases of F4MR. Among the most important findings that emerged we highlight the need to fit the needs of as many people as possible while keeping rehabilitation robot devices user friendly. Furthermore, devices should be light weight and easily transportable and storable, especially if home-based use is considered. It is also key to make the robot engaging and motivating for the patients. Finally devices able to perform a wider range of well implemented exercises, instead of a single one, seem preferable.

Based on the results of the literature mapping study a F4MR requirements elicitation instrument is being developed, to be disseminated within the F4MR consortium to gather the largest sample of Italian national respondents to date. Results of such study will be pivotal to inform the following key phases of the project.

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